

A NEW N-FOLD FLIP-FLOP WITH OUTPUT ENABLE

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ABSTRACT

With the evolution of the semiconductor industry and the continuous growing demands for high performance VLSI circuit, the aggressive scaling in feature size and high integration density along with the high operating frequencies make power consumption and digital noise in modern analog and digital devices one of the top concerns of Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) circuit design. In this paper we delve into the design of n-fold flip-flops with output enable. A new n-fold flip-flop exploiting the clock gating technique for both outputs enabling and power saving is presented. To evaluate its performance, an octal flip-flop was built according to the new proposed structure and compared to the main octal flip-flops used today. The different flip-flops were implemented in STMicroelectronics 65 nm process technology and simulated for the worst case condition where the switching activity is maximal. Post layout simulation showed that the new circuit provides the same functional performances as conventional solutions with significantly less power consumption, area and digital noise.

KEYWORDS

Flip-flops; Output enabling; Low power design; Clock gating

1. INTRODUCTION

The advancements in the field of CMOS technology have promoted a continuous increase in the density of integration as well as in the frequency of operation of the VLSI ICs. As technology advances push for smaller devices and faster operations, power consumption and noise become severe problems when designing high-speed ICs. These challenging concerns are mainly due to the excessive switching activity in the chip that keeps increasing proportionally to the frequency augment and the number of transistors. According to Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors [1], dynamic power is expected to keep being a significant portion of the total power consumption in the coming CMOS systems which represents a grand challenge that must be overcome. It has been shown that a significant portion (30-60%) of the total power consumption is dissipated in the clock distribution network and flip-flops that constitute ubiquitous elements for digital CMOS ICs design [2]. This power is dissipated in form of heat and radiation which complicate further the design of the circuit. Since the leakage current augments with temperature, the inefficient package cooling technologies used today contribute to drastically boost the power dissipation. Clock-gating is a simple and effective method for decreasing dynamic power consumption. As the dynamic power is proportional to frequency and the number of transistors, it can be lowered by the clock gating technique that reduces the switching activity of the consuming signal transitions. Further, clock gating contributes also to mitigate the simultaneous switching, hence, minimizing the switching noise levels and extending the circuit's life.

There are many n fold flip-flops with controllable outputs that have been reported in the literature. Some of these flip-flops have a small data-to-output delay and are quite good at being

high performance. However, as frequency increase is required, their design and optimization become crucial from both noise and power consumption standpoint. In this paper, a novel n fold flip-flops based on the concept of clock gating is proposed. The circuit consumes less power, results in less digital noise and takes small layout area. The proposed circuit is compared to the conventional and widely used flip-flop (DFF) circuits manufactured and sold today. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives an overview on the sources of power consumption in CMOS devices. The concept of clock gating for power saving is explained in sections 3. In section 4, the two well-known n fold flip-flops with output enable are reviewed. Section 5 presents the new n fold flip-flops and explains its operation and technique to mitigate power consumption and alleviate the noise. In section 6, the implementation and the extensive simulation of individual flip-flops as well as their comparisons are presented. Finally, section 7 concludes the paper.

2. SOURCES OF POWER CONSUMPTION IN CMOS CIRCUITS

CMOS technology has rapidly embraced the field of digital integrated the field of analog and digital integrating circuit since their invention. In recent years there has been an increasing demand for high-speed and at low power digital circuits. With technology shrinking and high clock frequency utilization, power consumption becomes a crucial design problem. In embedded system, this problem is exacerbated by the decent battery technology that limits the circuit's autonomy to only few hours. Therefore, it is very important to reduce at maximum the power consumption of a digital circuit while maintaining its performances as they are. The power consumed by a digital CMOS circuit is given by the relation (1):

$$P_{avg} = I_{leakage} \cdot V_{dd} + I_{sc} \cdot V_{dd} + (C_L \cdot V \cdot V_{dd} \cdot f_{clk} \cdot \alpha) \quad (1)$$

The relation shows that the overall power consumption is partitioned in 3 main components where the first represents the static power caused by the leakage current $I_{leakage}$. The second component is the short circuit power caused by the short circuit current I_{sc} flowing from power supply V_{dd} to ground during the simultaneous conducting of the CMOS transistors. Finally, the last component is the switching power due in essence to capacitive charge/discharge and which is regarded as a non trivial source of power dissipation in digital circuit. In the switching power term, C_L represents the effective switched loading capacitance, f_{clk} is the clock frequency and V is the voltage swing of the signals. The coefficient α denotes the switching activity that is none other than the probability of the power consuming transitions. In CMOS devices the dynamic power consumption due to the short circuit current and load capacitance charge/discharge dominates the total power consumption. Though the static power keeps increasing with each new technology node generation, the dynamic power still constitute the main cause of power loss in VLSI CMOS devices. With the STMicroelectronics 65 nm CMOS technology, the dynamic power represents 60% of the total power losses (Fig. 1). This obliges designers to find solution capable to mitigate its effects on their design performances in order to provide low power devices aiming at longer battery life, a high reliability and avoiding the utilization of cooling devices.

Figure 1. Increasing Contribution of Leakage Power in STMicroelectronics CMOS technology.

3. CLOCK GATING FOR LOW-POWER CIRCUIT DESIGN

Looking at the relation (1), power consumption can be reduced by using different low power techniques at various design levels [3]. Since the last score and until recently, many researches focused on this issue and provided different efficient solutions such as energy recovery [4][5][6] and the well-known low power techniques [3][7]. Among these techniques, clock gating [8][9] is a popular low power technique allowing to reduce the dynamic power of a circuit at the logic level by decreasing the switching activity in the clocked elements and in the clock trees forming it. This can be done by deactivating the clock signal fed to the concerned circuits when these are no needed. The Fig. 2 shows the commonly used implementation of this technique at the logic level. The basic idea is simple and consists in letting or not the clock signal reach the DFF according to the state of a control signal CE. The gated clock signal is obtained by ANDing the clock signal with the signal SCE that represents the synchronized version of the control signal CE. This signal is used to obtain a glitch-free clock gating. Hence, when CE becomes high, the SCE signal becomes high at the next rising edge of the clock and the gated clock is passed to the clocked elements. Conversely, if CE goes back to low state, the SCE signal copies it at the next clock rising edge disabling the gated clock and forcing the clocked element to enter in standby mode. Applied to an entire system, this technique allows saving a considerable amount of power when the clock is deactivated.

Figure 2. Clock gating circuit.

4. CONVENTIONAL FLIP-FLOPS WITH OUTPUT ENABLE

The n fold flip-flops with output enable is an important building block in digital systems. It consists of a set of flip-flops which outputs can be whether opaque or transparent according to the state of a single control signal used to control the transparency of these outputs. On-chip and Off-chip applications utilize such circuits as bank registers to store data for a defined period of time. A wide selection of different n fold flip-flops with output enable can be found in the literature [10][11]. One solution widely used is the Mux based n fold flip-flop. As an example, the 74F378 circuit [12] commercialized by Philips Semiconductors is built based on this principle for data retention. The internal schematic diagram of this Hex D flip-flop with output enable is shown in Fig. 3. If the register must hold state and prevent the reading of the new data present at its input, each flip-flop output of the register is fed back into the flip-flop's input through a Multiplexer (Mux). Conversely, if a new data have to be copied by the output, the new data is routed to the flip-flop's input by the same Multiplexer whose select signal is used to decide whether the register has to hold the new data or recycles the existing data.

Figure 3. Hex D flip-flop with output enable.

The limits of the circuit are due to the utilization of a Multiplexer for each flip-flop to hold the data at the output. When the number of flip-flops is increased to enlarge the width of the register, the circuit area and its power consumption increase considerably. Furthermore, since the input and output data are steered by the Multiplexer, the delay introduced by data path to the input signal restricts the operation of this device only at low and moderate frequencies. Other solutions utilize Tri-State buffers to control the transparency of the register's output. This solution is used by STMicroelectronics to implement an octal flip-flop [13]. The register is built with eight flip-flops which outputs are controlled with dedicated non-inverting or inverting Tri-State buffer (Fig. 4). All these buffers share the same control signal which High/Low level decides the behavioural opaque/transparent mode of the buffers. The circuit is more useful when it employs non inverting buffers because of their ability to maintain information once buffers are deactivated. A non-inverting buffer consists of a Tri-State inverter in serie with a conventional inverter. Hence, when the control signal is active, the buffers are in transparent mode and the register outputs the same data present at the outputs of the flip-flops. If the control signal is disabled, the outputs of the first inverters of the buffers are at high impedance forcing the second inverters forming the buffers to hold the old data at their outputs.

Figure 4. Octal D flip-flop with output enable.

Compared to the previous solution, this circuit has less transistors count, consumes less power and can operate at high frequencies since it has a small input delay. However, for both these solutions, the flip-flops of the registers are permanently clocked regardless the transparency of the output. A huge amount of power is dissipated dynamically because of the continual switching of the transistor. Even if no new data is captured, the flip-flops are still clocked and the circuit keeps consuming power. This consumed power is essentially dynamic and is linearly proportional to the number of flip-flops. To lessen the dynamic power, conditional capture and conditional precharge [14][15] flip-flops can be used instead of using normal flip-flops. It has been shown that the application of conditional techniques can reduce the switching activity of the transistors and save more than 50% of the consumed power [16]. Eventually this helps also reduce the effect of switching on the circuit performance. Though conditional flip-flops are very efficient for dynamic power saving, their static power consumption remains high since a considerable number of transistors are required to design it. In addition, they take a large area on silicon when implemented and their design is complex if compared to other low power and high speed flip-flops such as True Single-Phase Clock (TSPC) flip-flops.

5. THE PROPOSED LOW-POWER AND LOW-NOISE FLIP-FLOPS WITH OUTPUT ENABLE

We propose an n fold flip-flop that takes advantages of clock gating to control the transparency of its output and reduce both its power consumption and digital noise. The circuit is constructed with a certain number of flip-flops and one unique clock gating module which main function is to control the clock fed to the flip-flops. According to the state of a control signal, the clock is passed or not to the clocked elements allowing the data retention at the output when the clock signal is disabled. Fig. 5 shows the controller's circuit. This controller is similar to that shown in Fig. 2 but has the advantage to introduce less latency to the gated clock hence minimizing skew when a high speed clock is used to synchronize the circuit. The timing diagram and the schematic diagram of an octal flip-flop implemented based on the proposed principle is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 5. Clock gating module.

The circuit consists of eight flip-flops and a clock controlling module and has two modes of operations. To update the outputs of the register, a ‘1’ logic must be present at the control signal EN. As long as this signal remains at high state, at each clock cycle the controller outputs a clock pulse that is transported by the Load signal to all the flip-flops forming the register. Therefore, the outputs of the register are transparent since the flip-flops loads the inputs at each rising edge of gated clock Load. If the EN signal passes to low state, the gated clock is deactivated and the flip-flops are no longer clocked preventing them to update their outputs. The outputs keep holding the last data that were stored in the flip-flop before deactivating the gated clock until this clock is activated again. During this mode the switching activity is reduced at maximum in the clock path

(a) Example of an octal flip-flop.

(b) Timing diagram.

Figure 6. The proposed n fold flip-flop.

as well as in the flip-flops and hence, the unnecessary dynamic power consumption is avoided. Another advantage of this solution is that it results in a small digital noise and allows a long life for the transistors since switching activity is reduced. This makes our improved conditional capture methods suitable for high-performance VLSI systems.

6. IMPLEMENTATION, SIMULATION AND COMPARISON

To prove the effectiveness of our approach for the design of high performances n fold-flip with controlled outputs we have chosen to compare the octal flip-flop of Fig. 6 to two other octal flip-

(a) The flip-flop circuit.

(b) Flip-flop power consumption vs frequency.

Figure 7. The modified version of the TSPC DFF proposed in [18].

flops among which one is a Multiplexer based while the other is a tri-state buffer based flip-flop. This allows obtaining a fair comparison since we can use the same flip-flop to build the different circuits. For this reason, the third approach that reposes on conditional capture/precharge flip-flop is eliminated in our comparison since it utilizes another kind of flip-flops. The three circuits were implemented at transistor level using the STMicroelectronics 65 nm lpsvt CMOS process technology. To do that, we designed and tested first a standard cell library containing a variety of logic gates and flip-flops. The library was designed according to a full custom design flow and the final circuits were constructed in the same manner but by taking the required circuit from the library which we instantiate in our design. The circuits were built using the TSPC flip-flop disclosed in [18] and which modified schematic is depicted in Fig. 7.

The modification that we introduced aimed to endow the circuit with an asynchronous reset. We used the minimum transistor size for the implementation in order to minimize power consumption and achieve high-speed operations. Using a 1.1 V power supply and by sweeping the clock frequency and temperature, PLS simulation proved that the DFF is capable to operate correctly at frequency below 9 GHz for temperatures ranging from -70°C to 130°C. Fig. 9 presents the simulated PLS current dissipation at 27°C in the DFF implemented with 65 nm lpsvt CMOS transistors.

Our final three circuits were simulated using SpectreRF, a component of the Cadence Design Suite [17] with foundry supplied BSIM4 models. Using a 500 MHz clock signal, the simulation was performed at typical process corners, typical environment conditions, using a 1.1 V power supply and taking into account the parasitic components to accurately analyze the circuits. For critical power consumption measurement, the circuits were simulated in the worst case condition by using a switching activity $\alpha=1$. Fig. 8 illustrates the post layout simulation result of the proposed octal flip-flop. In the figure, the signal D represents the signal fed to all the inputs of the flip-flop, CLK represents the clock signal, C is the gating control signal, S is one output of the flip-flop and I is the current flowing through the power supply pin. The post layout simulation proved that the new octal flip-flop consumes much less power and results in much less current

Figure 8. Post layout simulation Waveforms.

Figure 9. Layout views of the implemented DFFs: (a) Tri-states buffer Octal DFF, (b) Octal Mux based DFF and (c) Proposed low-power Octal DFF.

spike during the active and sleep mode when compared to the other circuits (Fig. 8). Furthermore, the simulation showed that the circuit achieves 71 % power reduction when operating in the sleep mode. The circuit takes the smallest area and its layout drawing is very simple since the circuit has less transistor count and requires less metal wires. Fig. 9 shows the layout drawing of the three circuits while Table 1 summarizes the comparison between these circuits when outputs are enabled OE or disabled OD.

Power consumption and noise reduction depends on many implementation issues. In fact, it is proportional to the number of flip-flops used, the voltage swing, the power supply and the testbench stimulus as well as the frequency of operation of the circuits. In addition, it depends on the transistor sizes which may require to be enlarged when equal rise/fall time and particular logical effort are required. The obtained results are for a one byte bit flip-flop and eventually they will provide an enhanced gain in term of power consumption, noise reduction and area when the proposed architecture is used to design bigger flip-flops with an extended number of bytes. Moreover, the power consumed in the proposed circuit can be less than that was measured. In fact, it can be further reduced by eliminating the synchronizing flip-flop of the clock controller that was used just to avoid the appearing of glitches in the gated clock. As a result, the control signal can fed directly the input of the Multiplexer and additional power and area can be saved. From another side, though the conditional capture/precharge based solutions utilize another kind of flip-flop, it is clear that the proposed circuit is better because the flip-flop that it encompasses has less transistor count and consequently it will consume less power and occupy lower area. All these advantages make our solution the right design options for low-power and high-performance applications.

Table 1. Flip-flop comparison.

Feature	Octal Mux based DFF	Tri-states buffer Octal DFF with enable	Proposed low-power Octal DFF
Max Current pics (μA)	390 (OE) 230 (OD)	350 (OE,OD)	300 (OE) 100 (OD)
Total power (W)	$2.76 \cdot 10^{-05}$ (OE) $1.25 \cdot 10^{-05}$ (OD)	$2.08 \cdot 10^{-05}$ (OE) $1.97 \cdot 10^{-05}$ (OD)	$2.07 \cdot 10^{-05}$ (OE) $5.96 \cdot 10^{-05}$ (OD)
Area (μm^2)	244.42585	179.52	168.4087
Metals Layers	3	3	2

7. CONCLUSION

A new n-fold flip-flop circuit with controllable output is presented in this paper. By exploiting the clock gating technique for both output control and switching activity reduction, the circuit introduces low noise and provides the ability to mitigate power consumption when its outputs are opaque. An octal flip-flop circuit build according to the new presented architecture was implemented in 65 nm STMicroelectronics process technology using 2 metal layers. Post layout simulation showed that the circuit has better power and digital noise performances when compared to the conventional similar industrial solutions. The circuit consumes about 20 μW under a 1.1 V power supply and occupies an area of about 168 μm^2 .

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